

Contents lists available at www.gsjpublications.com

Global Scientific Journal of Environmental Research

journal homepage: www.gsjpublications.com/gsjer

Utilization of Agro-Wastes to Produce Myco-Diesel Production

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15 Jun 2024,
Revised: 25 Jun 2024,
Accepted: 1 Jun 2024,
Online: 7 Jul 2024

Keywords:

oleaginous fungi : biodiesel –GC-
MASS

ABSTRACT

The current study was highlighted the use of oleaginous fungi isolated from different oil seeds which can be used as alternative to fossil fuels. Many countries are currently trying to find sources for this type of diesel in preparation for the post-petroleum phase because it is low cost and eco-friendly. Oleaginous fungal isolates grown on natural culture media from various types of natural media (peanut husks, apple peels and banana peels) in addition to yeast extract sucrose as an inexpensive carbon source in order to produce biodiesel production, the higher biomass of wet and dry weight values were obtained using, peanut husks firstly were recorded (32.00, 11.05) g/L for oleaginous fungal isolates *A. fumigatus* then followed apple peels was secondly, (20.60, 7.07) g/L and banana peels thirdly, (17.89, 5.98) g/L respectively. The height yield of lipids using peanut husks compared with the apple and banana peels and the control (80.54)%. The qualitative and quantitative chemical analysis of the lipids contents by Gas Chromatography GC-identified the presence of Palmitic acid, Oleic acids, Stearic acid, myristic acid and linoleic acid in Fatty Acid Methyl Ester (FAME) analysis of *A. fumigatus* showed the predominant of Saturated Fatty Acid (SFA) than Unsaturated Fatty Acid (USFA) this indicates that the fungal lipid obtained has the same properties of biodiesel.

1. Introduction

Fuels have been the main energy source for modern society since the Industrial Revolution. The increasing demands for energy, make us in a risk from loss of energy shortages because of low fossil fuel reserves. Therefore, the focus of many governmental and industrial efforts on exploring alternative renewable energy sources has become one of these alternative energy sources, which is biodiesel derived from microbes, especially fungi that can store large amounts of fat in their cells (Ozsoy *et al.*, 2015).

External carbon is converted by fungi metabolism into carbohydrates or hydrocarbons, and then into fats stored in a Triacylglycerids compound (Devaraj *et al.*, 2019) Oleaginous microorganisms are those that make up the total fat content within their cells at more than 20% of their biomass, include algae, fungi and bacteria. Therefore, lipid filamentous fungi enter as raw materials in the sustainable biodiesel industry, and they appear to be a good alternative to fossil fuels (Bhanja, *et al.*, 2014). Many fungal species are able to accumulate

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doi: [10.5281/gsjer.2024.12739696](https://doi.org/10.5281/gsjer.2024.12739696)

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fat and store intercellular such as *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Mortierella isabellina*, *Mortierella alliacea*, *Humicola lanuginosa*, *Trichoderma reesei*, *Mortierella vinacea* & *Mucor circinelloides* (Ines *et al.*, 2019) and isolates of *Fusarium graminearum* *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* *Trichoderma spp.*, *Mucor circinelloides*, *Gliocladium roseum* were registered as effective lipid accumulators (Ozsoy *et al.*, 2015 ; Shafiq *et al.*, 2021) .

The aim of this study is to focus on using biodiesel or fungus diesel as an alternative to fossil fuels through the use of microbes (fungi) to produce biodiesel, and to provide natural sources for the highest diesel production of oleaginous fungi by decomposing the biomass of fungi used as a substitute for fossil fuels that are racing Many countries find resources for preparation for the post-fuel phase at the lowest cost, in addition to being an eco-friendly , in spite of the scarcity of studies on biodiesel production by fungi, there are some studies that have been limited to studying the environmental conditions such as different of temperature , carbon and nitrogen and pH for the production of bio-diesel by oleaginous fungi , such as some species of the genus *Aspergillus* (Abu-Elreesh, & Abdelhaleem 2014; Barbare *et al.*, 2021) and *Mucor circinelloides*, *Gliocladium roseum* isolated from various environmental sources such as soil and water (Magdum *et al.*, 2015)

2. Material and Methods

Screening Fungal Isolates for Lipid Production

To select the highest lipid producer among them, *Aspergillus fumigatus* isolates after isolated from different oil seeds(black grain , sesame and mustard) were cultured in basal medium containing a chromogenic substrate (Congo red). in g/L: 10g peptone, 5g NaCl, 0.1g Calcium chloride , 1ml castor oil, 15g agar, 0.5g Congo red with initial pH 6.0). Lipolysis was indicated by the appearance of clear zone of inhibition around the disc of inoculation. The diameters of the colonies and clearance zones were measured after 14 days (Haliru *et al.*, 2019).

Biomass and total lipid yields

The natural media were prepared with a weight of 50 g of peanuts husks, banana and apple dried peels separately after grinding and added to a quantity of distilled boiled water for 30 minutes, cooled and put in a mixer for 30 minutes, then filtered using a medical gauze and completed a volume of water distilled to 1 liter and pH adjusted to 6.0. 500 ml then added to a 1 liter flask after which sterilized with autoclave (121 °C and under pressure of 15 pounds / ² for 20 minutes). Inoculate the medium by adding 5 tablets of fungal isolate *A. fumigatus* and incubated for 14 days at 30 ° C, then follow the biomass extraction and dry weight of fungal isolate selective (Ajah & Shafeeq, 2016) and dry weight estimation as followed by (Shafiq *et al.*, 2021) and production of lipids .

Biodiesel analysis by gas chromatography

Total lipids were extracted from the dried biomass as mentioned in the previous paragraph, for the purpose of diagnosing the types of fatty acids. The process of analyzing methyl esters (FAMES) fatty acids was conducted using a method (Abu-Elreesh& Abdelhaleem , 2020) with some slight modifications. (FAMES) was produced by the esterification reaction consisting of. 2 ml of methanol with sulfuric acid (2.5% V / V H₂SO₄ / CH₃OH) as a catalyst added to 100 mg of raw fat extracted from the fungus producing fat. The reaction took 45 minutes at 90 ° C (water bath). Then 1 ml of H₂O and 2 ml of hexane were added. The (FAMES) were separated in the N-hexane layer and then centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 15 minutes to separate the aqueous layer from the hexane containing (FAMES), then transferred to a glass vial using a Pasteur pipette for the purpose of quantitative and qualitative assessment of fatty acids Using a gas chromatographic device after adding .1 mL of a mixture consisting of (KOH, 1% W / V methanol) and 1 mL of heptane alcohol. Gas chromatography (GC) analyzer (GC-17A model was used by Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan) with a chromatography data management system to analyze weight percentages of fatty acids.

3. Results and Discussion

Biomass and the total lipid yields

To determine the highest bio-mass and lipid yield of selected fungal isolate oleaginous fungi *A.fumigatus* ,figure-1- showed good biomass under the given carbon rich, nitrogen limiting conditions. The wet and dry weight of biomass obtained were the lowest value to banana peel medium (17.89 , 5.98) g/L while the total lipids percentages was 46.27% and the highest value to peanuts husks medium (32.00 , 11.05)g / L while the total lipids percentages was 80.54 %

compared with the control yeast extract sucrose medium (Figure -1). this natural medium was considered a good medium for production of lipid because the best carbon source for lipid accumulation in *A.fumigatus* ..Different types of agro-industrial wastes have been suggested as prospective nutritional sources for microbial cultures. Since the most abundant residue from agricultural crops is lingo cellulosic biomass, by product has been given top-priority consideration as a source of biomass for biodiesel production. (Gong *et al* ., 2014 ; Karisson *et al.*, 2016 ; Shafiq,2017)

Figure -1-- The biomass(wet and dry) of *Aspergillus fumigatus* on **A&a** appel: peel ; **B&b** : banana peel; **C&c**: peanut husks

Table 1: Biomass wet and dry weight (g/L) and Total Lipids percentage of oleaginous fungi growing on Natural liquid medium

Treatments	Biomass wet weight (g/L)	Biomass dry weight (g/L)	Total Lipids percentage to Biomass dry weight (%)
Yeast Extract Sucrose (Control)	23.49	8.99	72.34
Peanut husks	32.00	11.05	80.54
Apple peels	20.60	7.07	60.65
Banana peels	17.89	5.98	46.27

Biodiesel Production and Analysis by Gas Chromatography

The biodiesel produced from oleaginous fungi *A.fumigatus* was analyzed by gas chromatography, as shown in figures (2,3,4,5) the types with percentages of fatty acid after transesterification process of lipids extracted from fungal isolates culturing on yeast extract sucrose the control compared with three different natural liquid media peanut husks , apple peels then banana peels .The results of fatty acid methylesters (FAMES)analyzing showed the permanent of Palmitic acid, or hexadecanoicacid , the most common fatty acid (saturated)found in all treatments . Its chemical formula is

$\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{14}\text{COOH}$ which is considered a major component of biodiesel ,then oleic acid (C18: 1n9c) and linoleic acid (C18: 2n6c) from unsaturated fatty acids, oleic acid $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_7\text{CH}=\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_7\text{COOH}$ or octadecenoic acid is an unsaturated fatty acid that is the most widely distributed in nature, in addition to linoleic acid is a polyunsaturated also octadecenoic acid .the latest was myristic acid, also called tetradecanoic acid, is a common saturated fatty acid (Shin *et al.*, 2015) . the presence of both saturated and unsaturated fatty give more favorable properties of biodiesel .These results were agreement with many studies (Abu-elreesh &Abdelhaleem , 2020; Shafiq &Ali ; Papanikolaou ,2019).

Figure(2): Quantitative and qualitative analysis of total lipids of *Aspergillus fumigatus* in liquid medium YES by GC devise

Figure (3): Quantitative and qualitative analysis of total lipids of *Aspergillus fumigatus* in liquid medium banana peel by GC devise

Figure(4): Quantitative and qualitative analysis of total lipids of *Aspergillus fumigatus* in liquid medium apple peel by GC devise

figure (5): Quantitative and qualitative analysis of total lipids of *Aspergillus fumigatus* in liquid medium peanuts husks by GC devise

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